

Irreversible Partial Demagnetization Analysis for Different Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor Rotor Topologies

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Abstract— This paper analyzes the impact of irreversible partial demagnetization on the performance of four PMSM topologies. These topologies, namely Surface-mounted Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (SPMSM), Halbach Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (HPMSM), Inset Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (IPMSM), and Spoke Interior Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (SIPMSM), are designed under the same general specifications and constraints. The analysis focuses on healthy and partially demagnetized motors' electromagnetic torque, back-EMF, and permanent magnet magnetic flux density. The findings provide insights into the aspects that need to be considered for further development of online detection, identification, and quantification of the extent of demagnetization.

Index Terms—irreversible partial demagnetization, Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors, fault diagnosis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to their high power density, permanent magnet synchronous motors (PMSM) are used in various applications, including electric vehicles, wind energy, and home and industrial appliances [1]. However, the performance of the PMSM may be reduced due to different faults [2]. These should be detected early to prevent further damage [3]. The faults in PMSM can be classified into mechanical faults (eccentricity and bearing faults), electrical faults (stator winding faults), and magnetic faults (demagnetization faults) [2]-[3]. Detection of rotor permanent magnet demagnetization is critical in PMSMs due to the substantial cost of the permanent magnets, which constitute approximately 50% of the total machine cost [5].

The demagnetization of PMs in a PMSM can be partial or uniform [1], [4] and [5]. During fault conditions, such as operating stress, high temperatures, and the presence of inverse magnetic fields, partial demagnetization can occur [1], [6], and [7]. Consequently, irreversible partial demagnetization in magnets degrades the machine's rated parameters [8]. In addition, it leads to an increase in vibration, coil temperature, and noise, as well as reduced torque.[9]-[10].

In [8], it is stated that the impact of the magnetomotive force resulting from armature interaction, which is related to the amplitude of the stator currents, can lead to partial demagnetization of PMs situated in the motor. This partial demagnetization of the magnets results in a permanent reduction of the main magnetic flux in the machine. The onset of irreversible demagnetization initiates at the trailing edge of the pole and gradually propagates forward over a period of time. This phenomenon occurs predominantly due to the influential role played by the q-axis component of the initial current in the process of irreversible partial demagnetization [11]. Consequently, the generated electromagnetic torque and motor power are reduced. It is important to note that operating the motor with a magnetic flux lower than the rated value increases current, which in turn induces increased power loss and temperature in the magnets. This condition accelerates the fault progression by increasing the likelihood of further demagnetization.

This paper analyses and compares the impact of operation irreversible partial demagnetization on the performances of four PMSM topologies due to changes in permanent magnet properties. The PMSM topologies were designed with identical specifications and constraints, which include the stator outer diameter, number of turns per phase, air gap size, and volume of permanent magnets on the rotor. This work aims to lay the groundwork for developing techniques and solutions that allow for improved online detection, localization, and quantification of the demagnetization level in permanent magnets (PM) across different permanent magnet synchronous motor (PMSM) configurations. In addition, the analysis involves examining the impact of the irreversible partial demagnetization on both the electromagnetic torque and back-EMF.

The paper's structure is as follows: Section II discusses the studied PMSM topologies and theoretical considerations. Section III covers the implementation of partial demagnetization. Section IV focuses on the analysis and discussions of partial demagnetization. Finally, the conclusion of the paper is provided in section V.

II. PMSM TOPOLOGIES AND THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The cross-sections of the analyzed PMSMs are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Four types of PM rotors and magnetization directions in black color.

Fig. 2. Three-phase stator winding layout of studied PMSM: U-phase (red), V-phase (green), W-phase (blue).

The research focuses on 3-phase PMSM topologies with eight poles and 18 slots. Fig. 2 provides an overview of the configurations of the examined stator windings. These stator windings are labeled U, V, and W, and each winding comprises six coils. The winding is structured with two layers: a coil pitch of 2, a pole pitch of 2.25, and a winding factor of 0.617.

The motors are designed according to the electrical and geometrical specifications presented in Table I.

TABLE I. DESIGN PARAMETERS OF PMSM

parameters	Value
Rated speed	4500 rpm
Rated power	2200 W
Rated torque	4.671 Nm
Rated power factor	0.9
Number of phases	3
Pole pairs, p	4
Maximum DC supply voltage	72 V
Number of slots	18
Stack height	48 mm
Stator outer diameter	96 mm
Rotor outer diameter	25.51 mm
Rotor PM volume	15170 mm ³
Airgap thickness	0.5 mm

The electromagnetic torque of PMSM can be calculated by:

$$T_e = \frac{3}{2} * p * [\Psi_{PM} * i_q + (L_d - L_q) * i_q * i_d] \quad (1)$$

Where i_d and i_q , are the direct and quadrature currents, respectively, L_d and L_q , are the direct and quadrature inductances, respectively, and Ψ_{PM} is the rotor's permanent magnet flux linkage. The total torque of the PMSM is the sum of the magnetic torque (T_m), generated by the interaction between the rotor's magnetic field and the stator's rotating magnetic field, and the reluctance torque (T_{rel}), generated by the asymmetry of the magnetic circuit in the d-axis and q-axis [12]. Both components of the electromagnetic torque in PMSM can be obtained as follows:

$$T_m = \frac{3}{2} * p * \Psi_{PM} * i_q \quad (2)$$

$$T_{rel} = \frac{3}{2} * p * (L_d - L_q) * i_q * i_d \quad (3)$$

For surface-mounted PMSM, the reluctance torque is equal to zero because $L_d = L_q$. However, in interior PMSM, the reluctance torque is different from zero because $L_d \neq L_q$. As this study focuses on the demagnetization of the magnets, it is clear that reducing the permanent magnet flux linkage reduces the torque's amount. Another component is the q-axis current; its change contributes to changes in the motor's torque. The back-EMF $e_{ph}(t)$ for one phase is derived by applying Faraday's law of induction.

$$e_{ph}(t) = - \frac{d\Psi_{ph}(t)}{dt} \quad (3)$$

Where Ψ_{ph} is the phase flux linkage that comprises both the rotor's permanent magnet flux linkage and the flux generated by the phase current flowing in the windings and the time, t . The value of induced back-EMF, $e_{ph}(t)$ is affected when the magnetic material is demagnetized because induced back-EMF depends on the rotor's permanent magnet flux linkage.

Torque ripple content (T_{ripple}) can be expressed as follows:

$$T_{ripple}(\%) = \frac{T_{max} - T_{min}}{T_{avg}} \quad (4)$$

Where; T_{max} is the maximum instantaneous torque; T_{min} is the minimum instantaneous torque and T_{avg} is the average electromagnetic torque.

The magnetic flux density of PMSM in the air gap can be calculated by:

$$B_{ag} = \frac{B_r * l_m}{l_m + \mu_r * g} \quad (5)$$

Where; B_{ag} is the magnetic flux density of PMSM in the air gap; B_r is the remanent flux density of the permanent magnet (T); μ_r is the relative permeability of the permanent magnet, l_m is the length of the permanent magnet, and g is the air gap length. The air gap flux density decreases when the remanent flux density of the permanent magnet is reduced or eliminated due to demagnetization. Additionally, the length of the magnet is directly proportional to the air gap magnetic flux

density, which means that the demagnetization of the magnet segment also decreases the air gap magnetic flux density. Both the length of the magnet and the remanent flux density contribute to the amount of the air gap magnetic flux density.

The efficiency, η of PMSM can be calculated as:

$$\eta = \frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} \times 100\% \quad (6)$$

Where, P_{out} is the mechanical power output, and P_{in} is the electrical power input. The efficiency of PMSM changes as the iron and copper losses change; with the increase in the losses, the motor's efficiency decreases.

III. PARTIAL DEMAGNETIZATION IMPLEMENTATION

In this paper, the study of partial demagnetization is presented. It is found that the trailing edge of the motor magnets can experience partial demagnetization due to a positive current, i_{sq} , resulting from an overload torque. This fault impacts the distribution of the magnetic field in the air gap of the PMSM[13]. The simulation for healthy magnets and partially demagnetized magnets in each PMSM rotor topology was carried out and compared using the finite element method (FEM). The partial demagnetization was modeled by demagnetizing a portion of the magnetic material from the edge of the rotor magnets, as depicted in Fig. 3. The flux lines indicate the orientation of the magnetic flux density, where a higher density of lines indicates a strong magnetic flux density. In Fig. 3, the demagnetized portion is in violet color. It is evident that the demagnetized portion of the magnet does not generate magnetic flux density, as it ceases to be a magnetic material.

(d)

Fig. 3. The demagnetized edges of permanent magnets in PMSM Topologies; (a) PMSM, (b) IPMSM, (c) Halbach PMSM, (d) SIPMSM

IV. PARTIAL DEMAGNETIZATION RESULTS ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation for each motor topology is carried out under rated conditions, including a rated current of 40.45 A and a rated speed of 4500 rpm. Tables II, III, IV, and V present the RMS values of the back-induced electromotive force (EMF) and magnetic flux density in the air gap (B_δ), the average value of the electromagnetic torque (T_{avg}), torque ripple (T_{ripple}), and the motor efficiency (η). Meanwhile, Fig. 4, Fig. 7, Fig. 10, and Fig. 13 depict the back-induced EMF of one phase, and Fig. 4, Fig. 7, Fig. 10, and Fig. 13 illustrate the electromagnetic torque of the motor. The horizontal dotted lines in Fig. 5, Fig. 8, Fig. 11, and Fig. 14 represent the value of the average electromagnetic torque. Fig. 6, Fig. 9, Fig. 12, and Fig. 15 also represent the magnetic flux density in the air gap.

A. SPMSM topology

TABLE II. TORQUE, BACK-INDUCED EMF, MAGNETIC FLUX DENSITY, AND EFFICIENCY FOR SPMSM TOPOLOGY

SPMSM Topology		PARAMETERS				
		T_{avg} (Nm)	T_{ripple} (%)	RMS EMF (V)	B_δ (T)	η (%)
SPMSM	Healthy PM	4.683	7.8	27.15	0.67	94.32
	Demagnetized	4.403	18.7	25.41	0.63	94.00

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4. Induced Back EMF versus Time of SPMSM Topology in Healthy and Demagnetized Permanent Magnet

Fig. 5. Torque vs Time; Comparison between Healthy and Demagnetized Permanent Magnet in SPMSM Topology

Fig. 6. Air gap flux density of the Healthy and Demagnetized Permanent Magnet in SPMSM Topology

Table II presents the outcomes of both healthy and partially demagnetized permanent magnets of SPMSM. The values shown in Table II indicate that the average electromagnetic torque, RMS value of induced EMFs, air gap magnetic flux density, and motor efficiency differ in both cases (both SPMSM with healthy and partially demagnetized PM). The results of irreversible partial demagnetization in SPMSM confirm that this fault affects the motor's performance. The comparison of average torque shows that the value of average torque of healthy PM decreases by almost 6% (from 4.683Nm to 4.403Nm), while the RMS value of induced EMF decreased by nearly 6.4% (from 27.15 volts to 25.51 volts). These changes are caused by the decrease in magnetic properties of the permanent magnets due to the partial demagnetization of PM. The air gap magnetic flux density also decreases due to the irreversible partial demagnetization in the permanent magnet, from 0.67 tesla to 0.63 tesla. Additionally, the torque ripple in the partial demagnetization fault increases by more than 139% in SPMSM (from 7.8% to 18.7%, see Table II).

B. HPMSM topology

TABLE III. TORQUE, BACK-INDUCED EMF, MAGNETIC FLUX DENSITY, AND EFFICIENCY FOR HPMSM TOPOLOGY

HPMSM Topology		PARAMETERS				
		T_{avg} (Nm)	T_{ripp} (%)	RMS EMF (V)	B_{δ} (T)	η (%)
HPMSM	Healthy PM	4.408	9.2	25.29	0.62	94.24
	demagnetized	4.171	12.4	23.79	0.60	93.93

Fig. 7. Induced Back EMF versus Time of HPMSM Topology in Healthy and Demagnetized Permanent Magnet

Fig. 8. Torque vs Time; Comparison between Healthy and Demagnetized Permanent Magnet in SPMSM Topology

Fig. 9. Air gap flux density of the Healthy and Demagnetized Permanent Magnet in HPMSM Topology

The results presented in Fig. 7, Fig. 8, Fig. 9, and Table III of the Halbach Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (HPMSM) confirm that the irreversible partial demagnetization fault significantly impacts the motor's performance. The average torque of a healthy PM decreases by approximately 5.4% (from 4.408 Nm to 4.171 Nm), while the RMS value of induced EMF decreases by about 5.9% (from 25.29 volts to 23.79 volts). These changes are directly attributable to the partial demagnetization of PM fault. The air gap magnetic flux density also decreases because of the irreversible partial demagnetization in the PM, going from 0.62 tesla to 0.60 tesla. Furthermore, the torque ripple in the partial demagnetization fault increases by more than 34.9% in SPMSM (from 9.2% to 12.4%, as seen in Table III).

C. IPMSM topology

TABLE IV. TORQUE, BACK-INDUCED EMF, MAGNETIC FLUX DENSITY, AND EFFICIENCY FOR IPMSM TOPOLOGY

IPMSM Topology		PARAMETERS				
		T_{avg} (Nm)	T_{rippl} ϵ (%)	RMS EMF (V)	B_{δ} (T)	η (%)
IPMSM	Healthy PM	4.673	12.9	27.88	0.72	94.14
	demagnetized	4.362	24.6	25.91	0.69	93.67

Fig. 10. Induced Back EMF versus Time of IPMSM Topology in Healthy and Demagnetized Permanent Magnet

Fig. 11. Induced Back EMF versus Time of HPMSM Topology in Healthy and Demagnetized Permanent Magnet

Fig. 12. Air gap flux density of the Healthy and Demagnetized Permanent Magnet in IPMSM Topology

The results in Fig. 10, Fig. 11, Fig. 12, and Table IV of the Inset Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor topology confirm that the irreversible partial demagnetization fault significantly affects the motor's performance. In comparing the average torque, it is evident that the value of average torque in a healthy PM has decreased by approximately 6.7% (from 4.673 Nm to 4.362 Nm). Similarly, the RMS value of induced EMF decreases by around 7.1% (from 27.88 volts to 25.91 volts). The partial demagnetization of the PM fault

causes the changes. It is worth noting that the air gap magnetic flux density also decreases from 0.72 tesla to 0.69 tesla due to the irreversible partial demagnetization in the permanent magnet. Furthermore, the torque ripple in the case of partial demagnetization fault has increased by more than 90.7% in IPMSM (from 12.9% to 24.6%, as shown in Table IV).

D. SIPMSM topology

TABLE V. TORQUE, BACK-INDUCED EMF, MAGNETIC FLUX DENSITY, AND EFFICIENCY FOR SIPMSM TOPOLOGY

SIPMSM Topology		PARAMETERS				
		T_{avg} (Nm)	T_{rippl} ϵ (%)	RMS EMF (V)	B_{δ} (T)	η (%)
SIPMSM	Healthy PM	3.867	14	26.43	0.68	92.00
	demagnetized	3.646	18.7	24.93	0.58	92.62

Fig. 13. Induced Back EMF versus Time of SIPMSM Topology in Healthy and Demagnetized Permanent Magnet

Fig. 14. Torque vs Time; Comparison between Healthy and Demagnetized Permanent Magnet in SIPMSM Topology

The results in Fig. 13, Fig. 14, Fig. 15, and Table V of the Spoke Interior Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (SIPMSM) confirm that the irreversible partial demagnetization fault has a negative impact on the motor's performance. The comparison of average torque shows a decrease of almost 5.7% in the value of average torque for a healthy PM (from 3.867 Nm to 3.646 Nm), while the RMS value of induced EMF decreased by almost 5.7% as well (from 26.43 volts to 24.93 volts); the partially demagnetized PM fault causes these changes.

The air gap magnetic flux density decreases due to irreversible partial demagnetization in the PM, from 0.68 tesla to 0.58 tesla. Furthermore, the torque ripple in the partial demagnetization fault has increased by more than 33.6% in SPMSM (from 14% to 18.7%, as shown in Table V).

Fig. 15. Air gap flux density of the Healthy and Demagnetized Permanent Magnet in SIPMSM Topology

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study shows that permanent magnets lose their magnetic properties when they undergo irreversible partial demagnetization. Regarding electromagnetic torque, the results for SPMSM and IPMSM show that the average torque values are 4.683 Nm and 4.673 Nm, respectively, which reach the value of the rated torque under a healthy permanent magnet (PM) state (4.671 Nm). However, the average torque values for HPMSM and SIPMSM do not reach the rated torque (4.408 Nm and 3.867 Nm, respectively). This difference in torque is due to the position and shape of the magnets in each topology. However, despite the presence of partial demagnetization in PMs, the values of electromagnetic torque in all topologies decrease as follows: SPMSM (6%), HPMSM (5.4%), IPMSM (6.7%), and SIPMSM (5.7%).

Additionally, all topologies experience an increase in torque ripple, which leads to vibration and noise during motor operation. Among the topologies, SPMSM is the most affected by partial demagnetization, with a 139% increase in torque ripple. IPMSM follows this with a 90.7% increase, HPMSM with a 34.9% increase, and SIPMSM being the least affected, with a 33.6% increase in torque ripple. Furthermore, the induced back electromotive force (EMF) and magnetic flux density in the air gap decrease when partial demagnetization is applied. Additionally, the efficiency of different motor topologies varies due to variations in motor losses and powers.

The findings of this study can be crucial for developing methods to detect and diagnose partial demagnetization in PMSMs. Analyzing critical parameters such as air gap magnetic flux density, EMFs, and torque ripple makes it possible to identify and quantify the degree of demagnetization. This, in turn, enables timely maintenance and extends the motor's lifespan. This study emphasizes the

significance of accurate design and monitoring to preserve the performance and efficiency of PMSMs, especially in the presence of demagnetization effects.

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